

**ONOMATOPOEIC WORDS IN CHINESE AND UZBEK:
MORPHOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION AND TYPOLOGICAL
COMPARISON**

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Abstract

Onomatopoeic words, as a linguistic term, have a history extending over several millennia in world linguistics. As a phenomenon addressed within theories of language, onomatopoeia occupies an important position in the linguistics of every language. This article considers how onomatopoeic words have been investigated by scholars in Chinese and Uzbek, analyses their place within the grammatical systems of both languages, and discusses their affiliation with particular parts of speech. In classifying onomatopoeic words, alongside the significance of parts of speech and issues of categorisation, the author outlines the views of a number of scholars and the differences between their approaches, including Uzbek linguists Usmonov, Qo'ng'urov, and Abdurahmonov, as well as Chinese linguists Ding Shengshu, Ma Zhen, and Wang Li. The paper also offers observations on the morphological classification of onomatopoeic words in both languages.

Keywords: morphology; onomatopoeic words; interjections; word formation; noun; adjective; numeral; verb.

Introduction

Onomatopoeic words constitute a distinct group, determined by the linguistic nature of language, and occupy a specific position within the system of parts of speech. For this reason, they have long remained one of the topics that has provoked debates and discussions among linguists worldwide. Regarding the etymology of onomatopoeia as a term, Liddell provides detailed information indicating that its

origins go back to Ancient Greek linguistics (Liddell & Scott, 1940: 388). The term onomatopoeia in European languages, derived from Latin and Greek, conveys the meaning of ‘naming’ and is interpreted as referring to words that arose from sounds existing in the world (Joseph, 2000: 403).

Onomatopoeic words may also be viewed as a historical category. Their emergence corresponds to periods in which human society acquired a greater ability to control the speech organs. In very early primitive stages, ideophonic or imitative words were very scarce, or virtually absent. In this regard, B. M. Yunusaliev notes: “In the lexicon of the Orkhon–Yenisei monuments, sound-imitative words have found no expression” (Yunusaliev, 1959: 156). R. Qo‘ng‘urov likewise agrees with this view.

From the second half of the twentieth century onwards, the issue of onomatopoeic words began to attract the attention of scholars. Through observation and analysis, researchers advanced various positions concerning these units. For instance, A. N. Kononov, in *Grammar of the Uzbek Language* (Kononov, 1948: 121), does not devote extensive attention to onomatopoeic words; in his grammar, only sound-imitative words are mentioned, and it is emphasised that they constitute a substantial part of the bases participating in word formation in Uzbek. Although no separate definition is provided, they are presented as one of the three semantic types of interjections (Qo‘ng‘urov, 1948: 226). In *Grammar of the Modern Turkish Literary Language* (Kononov, 1956: 72), however, he treats them as a separate part of speech. Thus, whereas in earlier works Kononov classifies imitative words as a type of interjection, by 1956 he concludes that they should be distinguished as an independent word class, and he states this position firmly in his work on modern Uzbek literary grammar.

Review of the Literature

Onomatopoeic words represent one of the most ancient and complex areas of linguistic inquiry, and their study has historically been conducted using different

scholarly approaches across periods. In global linguistics, this phenomenon can be traced back to Ancient Greek and Latin traditions. Liddell and other European scholars explained the etymology of the term onomatopoeia through the idea of ‘naming a sound’, relating it to imitative sounds that emerged in the earliest stages of human speech and to their role in language formation.

Within Turkology, the first studies devoted to imitative words began in the 1920s. Although they were initially treated within grammatical works as part of interjections, they later began to be analysed as an independent word class. In this respect, A. N. Kononov, A. G‘ulomov, U. Tursunov, J. Muxtorov, S. Mutallibov, S. Usmonov, and other Uzbek linguists made significant contributions.

Although Kononov does not discuss onomatopoeic words extensively in Grammar of the Uzbek Language, he nevertheless mentions them as one of the bases involved in word formation. Later, in Grammar of the Modern Turkish Literary Language (1956), he recognises imitative words as an independent part of speech. A. G‘ulomov likewise initially regarded them as a type of interjection, but in subsequent scholarly statements emphasised the necessity of distinguishing onomatopoeic words as a separate category.

The most substantial achievements in this direction are associated with R. Qo‘ng‘urov. He investigated the phonetic, lexical, grammatical, and stylistic features of onomatopoeic words in Uzbek in depth and published the monograph Ideophonic Words in Uzbek in 1966. In it, the author analyses the place of these words within the language system, their role in word formation, their semantic types, and their stylistic functions.

In Chinese linguistics, the study of onomatopoeic words began in the early twentieth century. Scholars such as Ma Zhen (马真), Ding Shengshu (丁声树), and Zhu Dexi (朱德熙) used the terms “象声词” or “拟声词” and recognised them as an independent component of Chinese morphology. Xing Fuyi (邢福义), in turn, distinguishes onomatopoeic words as a special ‘third type’, i.e. a special constituent

(特殊成分).

Overall, the analysis of the existing literature shows that, in both Uzbek and Chinese linguistics, onomatopoeic words were for a long time treated as interjections or stylistic units. In more recent scholarship, however, their morphological independence, grammatical formation, and semantic types have become separate objects of study. The present article aims to provide a comparative analysis of scholarly approaches in these two languages and to identify the morphological typology of onomatopoeic words.

Research Methodology

This study examines the morphological structure, grammatical formation, and categorisation of onomatopoeic words in Chinese and Uzbek. The main purpose is to determine the position of these units in both language systems and to identify similarities and differences in form, meaning, and function. The research employs comparative-typological, descriptive, morphological, and historical-comparative methods.

The theoretical basis of the study draws on classical scholarly works in Uzbek and Chinese linguistics. Alongside the views of Uzbek linguists A. N. Kononov, S. Mutallibov, U. Tursunov, R. Qo‘ng‘urov, G‘. Abdurahmonov, and Sh. Rahmatullayev, the study analyses the research of Chinese linguists Ma Zhen, Ding Shengshu, Zhu Dexi, Wang Li, Lü Shuxiang, and Zhang Jing. These sources are used to assess comparatively the place of onomatopoeic words within the language system, their grammatical properties, semantic categorisation, and stylistic functions.

As research material, the study draws on works such as Modern Uzbek Literary Language, Modern Uzbek: Morphology, Qo‘ng‘urov’s Ideophonic Words in Uzbek, as well as grammars of Chinese by Ding Shengshu, Zhu Dexi, Wang Li, Lü Shuxiang, and Zhang Jing. In addition, Liddell and Scott’s A Greek-English Lexicon and Joseph’s The American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language

are used as terminological foundations.

The novelty of the study lies in the fact that it offers, for the first time, a systematic comparative analysis of onomatopoeic words in Chinese and Uzbek. Their morphological typology, word-formation patterns, grammatical features, and role in categorisation are identified, and the stylistic and semantic aspects of these units are compared across the two languages. Furthermore, theoretical conclusions are developed concerning the formation of onomatopoeic words as an independent word class, their artistic and expressive function in discourse, and their functional relations within the grammatical system.

Analysis and Results

In his works, N. I. Ashmarin firmly maintains the view that all words in all languages derive from onomatopoeic words. In his view, at the earliest stages language consisted only of mimemes, and only later did articulated speech sounds develop from them. He argues that before speech sounds emerged from mimemes, language passed through a period of selecting and accumulating speech sounds and primary words. Ashmarin suggests that the reason we cannot identify the imitative origins of many modern names is that we no longer know which feature of an object gave rise to the mimeme that eventually became its fixed name (Ashmarin, 1948: 1). Therefore, he emphasises the need to study carefully those phenomena of animate and inanimate nature that may be reflected in onomatopoeic words. He further argues that, in order to uncover the origin of language and find its proto-forms, one should study facial expressions, gestures, bodily movements, and the natural sounds associated with them, as well as the 'languages' of birds and animals, and compare these with modern language (Qo'ng'urov, 1948: 7).

In his school textbooks and in *An Introduction to Uzbek Morphology*, A. G'ulomov treats onomatopoeic words as a type of interjection. However, in a report delivered at a republican conference in August 1957 on improving the teaching of Uzbek in schools, he explicitly notes the need to distinguish onomatopoeic words

as a separate type. U. Tursunov and J. Muxtorov (Tursunov & Muxtorov, 1960: 260), S. Mutallibov (Mutallibov, 1959: 239), and S. Usmonov (Usmonov, 1952: 5) also separate ideophonic words from interjections and treat them as an independent word class.

Drawing on long years of experience, Mutallibov published an article on onomatopoeic words in 1956 in Teachers' Newspaper. In that paper, both sound-imitative words and image-based words are referred to under the single term 'sound-imitative words', and both types are unified under one label. The paper contains some ambiguous points; however, in later essays (Mutallibov, 1959: 239) he introduced clarifications. Nevertheless, in both works certain confusions are observable when interpreting examples: in particular, sound-imitative words are sometimes conflated with words expressing images of motion or state. For example, his article classifies yaltiroq, yalt-yult, lim-lim, g'imir-g'imir as sound imitations, and his essays classify dikillamoq (Mutallibov, 1959: 212) likewise. These examples should be treated not as sound imitations, but as ideophones/imagistic (state-imitative) words.

Mutallibov combines sound-imitative and state-imitative words and defines them as follows: "Words formed by conventionally imitating sounds produced by the actions of animals, creatures, birds and insects, humans, and objects are called sound-imitative words" (Mutallibov, 1959: 210).

In Modern Uzbek, onomatopoeic words are briefly distinguished as a separate category under the term mimemes, although in some chapters they continue to be treated as interjections. In Tursunov and Muxtorov's *Modern Uzbek: Morphology*, onomatopoeic words are also examined briefly as a separate category. The authors define them as follows: "Onomatopoeic words are an imitation—a copy—of the sounds of persons, objects, and various living creatures, and of the images of motion and state received from the external world. Onomatopoeic words denote various voluntary or involuntary sounds and cries, as well as images of motion and state"

(Tursunov & Muxtorov, 1960: 260).

The authors divide onomatopoeic words into two types—sound-imitative words and image-based words—provide definitions, and illustrate them with examples. Accordingly, words formed by imitating various natural phenomena, the sounds of animals and humans, and images of motion and state are referred to as onomatopoeic words.

In *Modern Uzbek Literary Language* edited by G‘. Abdurahmonov and authored by E. Begmatov, onomatopoeic words are presented under the term “ideophonic words” and described in relatively greater detail. There, ideophonic words are defined as: “Words that arise through imitating the diverse sounds of the objective world and the image-like states of the movements of objects and phenomena are called ideophonic words.”

However, in *Historical Grammar of Uzbek: Phonetics, Morphology and Syntax* (Abdurahmonov, 2008: 75), onomatopoeic words are not listed among the parts of speech. The scholar divides parts of speech into lexical (independent) and functional (auxiliary) words. Independent words are, in turn, divided into nouns, verbs, and adverbs; nouns are divided into noun, adjective, numeral, and pronoun. Among auxiliary words he lists postpositions, conjunctions, particles, and, conditionally, interjections, but does not include onomatopoeic words.

Another Uzbek linguist, Shavkat Rahmatullayev, includes onomatopoeic words in grammatical description under the label “ideophonic units” (Rahmatullayev, 2006: 213). He defines an ideophonic unit as a symbolic representation—formed through linguistic units—of various surrounding sounds and of the appearance of motion and state. He also emphasises that there is a difference between onomatopoeia and ideophonic words.

In Uzbek linguistics, R. Qo‘ng‘urov’s contribution to the study of ideophonic (onomatopoeic) words is particularly substantial. His scholarly observations resulted in a series of articles, including “Some Observations on Onomatopoeic

Words in Uzbek” (Qo‘ng‘urov, 1960: 12), “On the Phonetic Features of Ideophonic Words in Uzbek Literary Language” (Qo‘ng‘urov, 1961a: 48), “On the Study of Onomatopoeic Words in Uzbek” (Qo‘ng‘urov, 1961b: 56), “On the Lexical Features of Ideophonic Words” (Qo‘ng‘urov, 1962: 32), and “Semantic Classification of Ideophonic Words in Modern Uzbek” (Qo‘ng‘urov, 1961c: 89). Synthesising issues such as their general description, structure, role in word formation, and phonetic, lexical, grammatical, and syntactic properties, he defended a candidate dissertation in 1962, and in 1966 published the monograph *Ideophonic Words in Uzbek* (Qo‘ng‘urov, 1966: 154). The work also includes a short glossary of ideophonic words.

In the section “From the History of the Study of Ideophonic Words”, Qo‘ng‘urov discusses the study of ideophonic words in Turkology and comments, to varying degrees, on the positions of Turkologists regarding these units.

Certain similarities and differences can be observed between Chinese and Uzbek scholars’ views on onomatopoeic words. To illustrate this, we consider selected scholarly positions.

Although the study of onomatopoeic words in China began somewhat later than the study of other parts of speech or grammatical units, it has passed through a gradual development over more than a century. As scholars sought to reveal the characteristics of these units, the first key issue became finding an appropriate term in Chinese to denote them. Different scholars used different labels. Ma Zhen (马真), in his grammatical work, notes that words imitating various sounds are referred to as “拟声词” or “象声词” (马真, 2015: 28), but he prefers the term “象声词” and uses it throughout. Ding Shengshu (丁声树), while not offering a separate definition, recognises onomatopoeic words as the final, tenth part of speech in Chinese morphology under the name “象声词” (丁声树, 1999: 6). Zhu Dexi (朱德熙), one of the most influential scholars to present a general account of theoretical

Chinese grammar, likewise does not provide a special definition, but lists them as an independent word class as “拟声词” (朱德熙, 1999: 50).

Wang Li proposes that onomatopoeic words arise by imitating various surrounding sounds; in writing and in language they do not necessarily reproduce the sound exactly. It is sufficient that they indicate a natural sound and that the listener understands it. He argues that such sounds are studied not by grammar but by stylistics; nevertheless, since their expression requires special linguistic form, they must be studied grammatically (王力, 2011: 96). He terms them “拟声词” and provides examples such as 哈哈, 咕咕, 咕咚, 哇, 嘟嘟.

As a result, leading Chinese linguists have divided into several groups regarding the question of assigning onomatopoeic words to parts of speech. Scholars such as Lü Shuxiang (吕叔湘), Zhang Jing (张静), and Liao Xudong (廖序东) proposed including onomatopoeic words within the category of adjectives and attempted to substantiate this view. Lü Shuxiang notes that the form of onomatopoeic words is very similar to the form of adjectives, and therefore recognising them as a sub-type of adjectives is not without grounds (吕叔湘, 1996: 14). Zhang Jing, in works such as *A Comparative Grammar of Ancient and Modern Chinese* and *A New Book on Modern Chinese*, classifies them as 象声形容词 and includes them among adjectives, emphasising that the grammatical functions and form of adjectives and onomatopoeic words are identical.

Conclusion

In both Chinese and Uzbek, onomatopoeic words are defined as words and are studied both grammatically and stylistically on the basis of their linguistic properties. Regardless of the language, onomatopoeic words convey meaning, and in some cases the overall meaning of a sentence is expressed precisely through the onomatopoeic element. If the onomatopoeic word is omitted, the meaning of the sentence may change or become insufficiently expressed.

We argue that defining onomatopoeic words as a term in linguistics should be carried out in accordance with the nature of each language. Words that in Uzbek also express state and image may, in other languages, not fall within the scope of onomatopoeic words and may perform different grammatical functions. From the above, it follows that onomatopoeia should be studied and analysed within terminology and morphology.

In Chinese and Uzbek, onomatopoeic words reflect the sounds and states of humans, animals, objects, and nature—that is, the entire soundscape and states of reality. The terms taqlid so‘zlar in Uzbek and 拟声词 in Chinese are used.

With regard to the morphological typology of onomatopoeic words, diverse viewpoints exist in both languages. In Chinese, we align with Ma Zhen’s view that onomatopoeic words belong to an independent part of speech. In Uzbek, given that onomatopoeic words do not answer interrogative questions, yet can function as sentence constituents, they should likewise be investigated within the framework of an independent word class.

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